

A novel approach for the synthesis of 5-methoxycarbonyl-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one-*N*⁴-oxides from *N*-chloroacetyl isatins

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Intramolecular cyclocondensation of *N*-(triethylaminoacetyl)isatin-3-oxime salts (**9a-d**) in MeOH and DMF yielded 5-methoxycarbonyl-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one-*N*⁴-oxides (**11a-d**) in moderate to good yields.

Ubiquity of 1,4-benzodiazepines in the chemical literature is doubtless a consequence of the multifarious biological responses which they elicit in combating the varieties of body ailments¹⁻⁷. The recent demonstrations^{8a,b} indicated that these compounds can serve as potential agents for the control and treatment of AIDS. This has created further interest in these compounds from yet another perspective.

The application of isatins in heterocyclic synthesis is well documented in the literature⁹. But its use in 1,4-benzodiazepine synthesis was not known until Ogata and Matsumoto published a brief note in 1976¹¹ showing that it could be employed in the synthesis of 5-substituted 1,4-benzodiazepines through the sequence of *N*-chloroacetylation followed by amination with methanolic solution of hexamine. Though this discovery has opened the possibility of using isatin derivatives in the synthesis of 1,4-benzodiazepines, but no attempt seems to have been made in the literature to examine its applications in the synthesis of other 1,4-benzodiazepine derivatives. The present paper describes a variation made in this novel approach to give the *N*⁴-oxide derivatives of 1,4-benzodiazepines (**11a-d**). The literature procedure¹² for the intramolecular cyclocondensation of **1** to **2** (Scheme 1) has been applied in the present work for the conversion of **9a-d** to **11a-d**.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

N-Chloroacetyl isatins (**6a-d**) were prepared by

chloroacetylation¹³ of the corresponding isatins (**5a-d**). Two approaches were conceived from **6a-d** for the preparation of the *N*⁴-oxides **11a-d**. In one of these, **6a-d** were treated with triethylamine in presence of KI to give the corresponding quaternary ammonium salts **7a-d**. Treatment of **7a-d** with hydroxylamine hydrochloride furnished the oximes **9a-d**, the thermal cyclocondensation of which with MeOH and DMF gave **11a-d** (Scheme 2). Formation of **9** from **7** was evident on the basis of the disappearance of the one of the cyclic C=O peaks (1775 cm⁻¹) of **7** and appearance of peaks for oxime (1650 cm⁻¹ due to C=N and 3360 cm⁻¹ due to OH) in its IR spectrum.

A variation in this methodology was applied on **6a-d** which consisted of preparing the oximes **8a-d** first and then treating the same in subsequent step with triethylamine and KI to give **9a-d** which in a likewise manner was subjected to the thermal cyclocondensation reaction in MeOH and DMF to give **11a-d**. We believe that conversion of **9a-d** to **11a-d** proceeds through the ring opened anti-oxime intermediate **10a-d**. Had *cis*-oxime been formed, it would have given benzoxadiazocine **12a-d**¹². Since there was no indication for its formation, the reaction probably occurred through anti-oxime only (Scheme 2).

Formation of **9** from **8** was indicated by the disappearance of the peak at 750–820 cm⁻¹ (due to C–Cl stretching vibration) of **8**, in IR spectrum of **9**. Peaks at 1650 cm⁻¹ due to C=N and 3360 cm⁻¹ due to OH showing the presence of oxime group in **9** were found to be absent in the IR spectrum of **11**, which clearly indicated its formation from **9**. Formation of **11** from **9** was further supported by the appearance of bands at 3222 and 1260 cm⁻¹ for NH group and *N*-oxide linkage respectively in the IR spectrum of **11**. ¹H NMR spectrum of **11** exhibited a singlet at δ 3.85 which was assigned to the methyl protons of the 5-methoxycarbonyl group. A singlet at δ 4.3 for two protons was attributed to

Note

Scheme 2

C₃ protons flanked between the two electronegative groups C=O on one side and C=N on the other side. A broad signal for one proton at δ 10.55 which exchanged with D₂O indicated the presence of NH group in the molecule. Presence of O=C-NH linkage indicated by IR and ¹H NMR in **11** clearly established that cyclization of **9** to **11** had taken place. **11** was converted to **13** (R = H) on removal of N-oxide function. Several procedures are known for deoxygenation of N-O function but we found the Childress procedure¹⁴, which involved the reaction with PCl₃ more convenient for deoxygenation of **11**. An authentic sample of **13** (R = H) was prepared using the literature method¹¹.

Disappearance of peak at 1260 cm⁻¹ (for N-O) in the IR spectrum of **13** clearly indicated that deoxygenation with PCl₃ had occurred. Further, the mixed melting point and

comparison of the spectral properties of this compound with authentic sample proved the formation of **13** from **11**. The mass spectra of **11a-d** and **13** exhibited correct *m/z* values for the molecular ion peaks. Fragment M-74 appeared as the base peak in **11a-d** which could arise by the loss of COCH₂O₂ from the parent ion. **13** showed a strong peak at M-58 owing to the loss of COCH₂O fragment. Physical and spectral data for all the compounds (**7a-d**, **8a-d**, **9a-d**, **11a-d** and **13**) were found to be consistent to the structures assigned to these molecules.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds was checked by TLC using the solvent systems benzene : methanol (9 : 1; v/v) and silica gel G as adsorbent. IR

spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP3-300 infracord spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a Varian EM 360 L spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 (EI) spectrometer.

Isatins (**5a-d**) were prepared using the reported procedure^{9,15}.

N-Chloroacetyl isatins (6a-d). General procedure : Isatin (**5a-d**; 0.068 mol) was vigorously refluxed with chloroacetyl chloride (70 ml, 0.089 mol) for 5 h and the mixture was cooled for 2 h in an ice-bath. The resulting solid was washed with ether (20 ml), air dried and recrystallized from ethyl acetate. **6a** (66%), m.p. 209° (Found : C, 53.32; H, 2.91; N, 6.91. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 53.69; H, 2.68; N, 6.26%); ν_{max} 1785 (cyclic C=O), 1745 (cyclic NC=O), 1720 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **6b** (67%), 185–187° (Found : C, 55.40; H, 3.25; N, 5.15. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 55.57; H, 3.36; N, 5.89%); ν_{max} 1775 (cyclic C=O), 1730 (cyclic NC=O), 1700 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **6c** (58%), 223–225° (Found : C, 52.15; H, 3.11; N, 5.28. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 52.07; H, 3.15; N, 5.52%); ν_{max} 1780 (cyclic C=O), 1740 (cyclic NC=O), 1705 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **6d** (47%), 130° (Found : C, 44.50; H, 1.34; N, 10.74. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 44.69; H, 1.86; N, 10.42%); ν_{max} 1760 (cyclic C=O), 1745 (cyclic NC=O), 1710 (acyclic C=O), 1550 (NO_2), 1345 cm^{-1} (NO_2).

N-(Triethylaminoacetyl)isatin iodides (7a-d). General procedure : A solution of *N*-chloroacetyl isatin (**6a-d**; 0.01 mol) in acetone (15 ml) was refluxed with triethylamine (10 ml) for 1 h. Diethyl ether was then added to the mixture and the precipitated mass was dissolved in DMF. Potassium iodide (1.6 g) was added and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. The solid obtained on addition of petroleum ether (100 ml) was dried and crystallized from methanol-ether. **7a** (66%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 46.40; H, 5.21; N, 6.80. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 46.15; H, 5.04; N, 6.73%); ν_{max} 1775 (cyclic C=O), 1745 (cyclic NC=O), 1725 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **7b** (72%), 176° (Found : C, 47.81; H, 5.50; N, 6.72. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 47.44; H, 5.34; N, 6.51%); ν_{max} 1770 (cyclic C=O), 1750 (cyclic NC=O), 1720 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **7c** (70%), 189° (Found : C, 46.00; H, 4.98; N, 6.00. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 45.73; H, 5.15; N, 6.27%); ν_{max} 1780 (cyclic C=O), 1740 (cyclic NC=O), 1730 cm^{-1} (acyclic C=O); **7d** (55%), 148° (Found : C, 41.50; H, 3.99; N, 9.23. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 41.64; H, 4.33; N, 9.11%); ν_{max} 1760 (cyclic C=O), 1730 (cyclic NC=O), 1710 (acyclic C=O), 1550 (NO_2), 1345 cm^{-1} (NO_2).

N-Chloroacetyl isatin-3-oximes (8a-d). General procedure : To a solution of sodium acetate (0.03 mol) in water

(10 ml) was added a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2.11 g, 0.03 mol) and *N*-chloroacetyl isatin (**6a-d**; 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 45 min at 60° and left overnight. A reddish yellow solid formed was washed with water, dried and recrystallized with 50% ethanol. **8a** (85%), m.p. 212° (Found : C, 50.25; H, 2.87; N, 11.64. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 50.32; H, 2.94; N, 11.74%); ν_{max} 1745 (cyclic NC=O), 1720 (acyclic C=O), 1650 (C=N), 3360 (OH), 790 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); **8b** (91%), 198° (Found : C, 52.19; H, 3.79; N, 10.97. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 52.28; H, 3.56; N, 11.09%); ν_{max} 1730 (cyclic NC=O), 1700 (acyclic C=O), 1645 (C=N), 3360 (OH), 799 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); **8c** (79%), 251° (Found : C, 49.19; H, 3.20; N, 10.33. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 49.16; H, 3.35; N, 10.43%); ν_{max} 1740 (cyclic NC=O), 1705 (acyclic C=O), 1650 (C=N), 3350 (OH), 800 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); **8d** (60%), 202° (Found : C, 42.35; H, 2.01; N, 14.85. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$ calcd. for : C, 42.33; H, 2.12; N, 14.81%); ν_{max} 1745 (cyclic NC=O), 1720 (acyclic C=O), 1660 (C=N), 3325 cm^{-1} (OH), 1550 (NO_2), 1345 (NO_2), 799 cm^{-1} (C–Cl).

N-(Triethylaminoacetyl)isatin-3-oxime iodides (9a-d). General procedure : Method A : To a solution of *N*-(triethylaminoacetyl)isatin iodide (**7a-d**; 0.005 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) was added a solution of sodium acetate (0.41 g, 0.005 mol) in water (5 ml) followed by a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.35 g, 0.005 mol) in ethanol (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 60° and left overnight. The reddish yellow solid settled was dried and recrystallized from methanol-ether. **9a** (85%), m.p. 163° (Found : C, 44.32; H, 5.41; N, 9.80. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 44.54; H, 5.10; N, 9.74%); ν_{max} 1740 (cyclic NC=O), 1715 (acyclic C=O), 1665 (C=N), 3350 cm^{-1} (OH); **9b** (89%), 172° (Found : C, 45.86; H, 5.32; N, 9.00. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 45.84; H, 5.39; N, 9.43%); ν_{max} 1730 (cyclic NC=O), 1710 (acyclic C=O), 1650 (C=N), 3345 cm^{-1} (OH); **9c** (80%), 169° (Found : C, 44.45; H, 5.32; N, 8.98. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 44.25; H, 5.20; N, 9.11%); ν_{max} 1735 (cyclic NC=O), 1710 (acyclic C=O), 1655 (C=N), 3355 cm^{-1} (OH); **9d** (76%), 198° (Found : C, 40.51; H, 4.01; N, 11.85. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{I}$ calcd. for : C, 40.33; H, 4.41; N, 11.76%); ν_{max} 1750 (cyclic NC=O), 1715 (acyclic C=O), 1660 (C=N), 3330 cm^{-1} (OH), 1550 (NO_2), 1345 cm^{-1} (NO_2). *Method B :* A solution of *N*-chloroacetyl isatin-3-oxime (**8a-d**; 0.005 mol) in acetone (10 ml) was refluxed with triethylamine (5 ml) for 1 h. Diethyl ether was then added to the mixture and the precipitated mass was dissolved in DMF. Potassium iodide (0.83 g, 0.005 mol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 45 min. The solid obtained on addition of petroleum ether (100 ml) was dried and recrystallized from methanol-ether. **9a**

(80%), **9b** (85%), **9c** (77%), **9d** (74%).

5-Methoxycarbonyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one-N⁴-oxides (11a-d). *General procedure*: *N*-(Triethylaminoacetyl)isatin-3-oxime iodide (**9a-d**; 0.005 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of dry methanol and DMF (1 : 1; v/v, 20 ml). The solution was heated under nitrogen on the steam bath for 6 h and then poured in 100 ml of water. The solid was washed with water and dissolved in benzene (a small amount of undissolved residue which remained was discarded). The benzene layer was washed with water and the residue obtained on removal of benzene was dissolved in chloroform and filtered over alumina (25 g). The alumina was washed with chloroform. The eluate was treated with animal charcoal, concentrated and recrystallized from methylene chloride. **11a** (56%), m.p. 243° (Found : C, 56.32; H, 4.17; N, 11.89. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 56.41; H, 4.27; N, 11.97%); ν_{\max} 3222 (NH), 1690 (cyclic C=O), 1735 (acyclic C=O of ester), 1260 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 10.55 (1H, s, br, exchanged with D₂O, CONH), 7.85–7.00 (4H, m, ArH), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃ of ester), 4.30 (2H, s, CH₂); *m/z* 234 (M⁺), 160 (base peak); **11b** (60%), 260° (Found : C, 58.09; H, 4.72; N, 11.20. C₁₂H₁₂N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 58.06; H, 4.84; N, 11.29%); ν_{\max} 3210 (NH), 1685 (cyclic C=O), 1725 (acyclic C=O of ester), 1255 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 10.54 (1H, s, br, exchanged with D₂O, CONH), 7.30–6.84 (3H, m, ArH), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃ of ester), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃ at C₇), 4.35 (2H, s, CH₂); *m/z* 248 (M⁺), 174 (base peak); **11c** (51%), 268° (Found : C, 54.60; H, 4.66; N, 10.72. C₁₂H₁₂N₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 54.55; H, 4.55; N, 10.61%); ν_{\max} 3220 (NH), 1680 (cyclic C=O), 1730 (acyclic C=O of ester), 1261 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 10.54 (1H, s, br, exchanged with D₂O, CONH), 7.13–6.96 (3H, m, ArH), 3.89 (3H, s, OCH₃ of ester), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃ at C₇), 4.29 (2H, s, CH₂); *m/z* 264 (M⁺), 190 (base peak); **11d** (44%), 264° (Found : C, 47.19; H, 3.39; N, 15.10. C₁₁H₉N₃O₆ calcd. for : C, 47.31; H, 3.23; N, 15.05%); ν_{\max} 3195 (NH), 1675 (cyclic C=O), 1720 (acyclic C=O of ester), 1265 (N-O), 1555 (NO₂), 1340 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); δ 10.52 (1H, s, br, exchanged with D₂O, CONH), 7.08–6.82 (3H, m, ArH), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃ of ester), 4.32 (2H, s, CH₂); *m/z* 279 (M⁺), 205 (base peak).

5-Methoxycarbonyl-1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (13) : To a solution of **11a** (0.47 g, 0.002 mol) in chloroform (15 ml) was added phosphorous trichloride (0.36 ml, 0.004 mol). The solution was heated under reflux for 30 min and poured into 1 N NaOH (30 ml). The organic phase was washed with NaCl solution and was passed through alumina (15 g). The residue obtained on evaporation of the solvent was crystallized from benzene to give 0.27 g of **13** (62%), m.p. 172–173° (lit.¹¹ 173–174°)

(Found : C, 60.23; H, 5.11; N, 12.61. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 60.55; H, 4.58; N, 12.84%); ν_{\max} 3220 (NH), 1690 (cyclic C=O), 1735 cm⁻¹ (acyclic C=O of ester); δ 10.55 (1H, s, br, exchanged with D₂O, CONH), 7.85–7.00 (4H, m, ArH), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃ of ester), 4.15 (2H, s, CH₂); *m/z* 218 (M⁺), 160 (base peak).

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